

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

MECHANISMS OF INTERGENERATIONAL TRANSMISSION IN A TRANSITIVE SOCIETY

Podborschi Angela

Ph. D student,

Free International University of Moldova,

Psychiatric Hospital in Chisinau

Abstract

The transformation processes occurring in contemporary society give rise to novel forms of interaction with reality, prompting significant changes across various life spheres, including social organization, communication methods, and socialization processes. This article examines the mechanisms of intergenerational transmission in transitional societies, contrasting them with traditional societies. Generations have historically been a crucial structural element of society, and in today's rapidly evolving landscape, fostering intergenerational connections is essential for societal integration, stabilization, and development.

Key theorists such as K. Mannheim, H. Ortega-i-Gasset, and Howe & Strauss have explored the concept of generation, emphasizing its socio-historical context and the psychological aspects of intergenerational relations. Modern research highlights the dynamics of intergenerational relationships, conflicts, and the impact of globalization and digital technologies on value systems. Findings indicate younger generations exhibit different value orientations, with increased educational attainment and shifts towards health consciousness, which influence their social and professional behaviors.

The concept of "digital socialization" reflects the significant role of the internet in shaping social interactions, particularly within transitional societies characterized by internal contradictions and rapidly changing contexts. The article also discusses the functions of intergenerational transmission, including the regulatory, informative, unifying, educational, referential, and supportive roles it plays in maintaining cultural heritage and values.

In this context, the challenges faced by intergenerational communication are examined, highlighting the necessity for new forms of engagement to bridge cultural gaps. The paper ultimately posits that while transitivity introduces complexities into intergenerational relations, it also opens avenues for evolving understanding and collaboration between generations.

Keywords: intergenerational transmission, values, socialization, generations, transitive society, mechanisms of intergenerational transmission, family, digital socialization.

The transformation processes taking place in society dictate new, previously unknown forms of interaction with reality. The challenges of modernity are causing changes in all spheres of life: in the organization, timing and processes of socialization, as well as in the methods of communication.

The value system is transformed, which in turn affects the mechanisms of transmission of experience, attitudes and values. This article analyzes the mechanisms of intergenerational transmission in transitive societies, and also considers differences in modes of intergenerational transmission in traditional and transitive societies.

Throughout the ages, generations have been a vital structural component of society. At present, in the global changes, the most urgent issue is the maintenance and strengthening of intergenerational ties, since the succession of generations is a necessary condition for integration, stabilization and development of society. The topic of generations is considered by many sciences: in sociology, philosophy, anthropology, psychology, culturology, political science.

The concept of «generation» was investigated by K. Mannheim (1928), H. Ortega-i-Gasset (1929), Howe, N., Strauss (1991), E. Bobrova (1997), A. Tolstoy (2000), T. Martsinkovskaya (2017). In modern research leading topics on issues of generations are intergenerational relations and conflicts: M.I. Postnikova

(2010); relationship between intergenerational relations and family functionality: M.A. Sizova (2012), M. Saprovinskaia (2013); directions of development of intergenerational communication and influence on them of modern processes occurring in society: D.I. Dubrov (2016), C. Dudin (2013); socio-psychological portraits and features of representatives of different generations: M. Begova, M. Iontseva (2016) and their relationship to work: A. Pantelev (2016). Mechanisms of interstellar transmission investigated by Barni (2009) Schonpflug (2001), Trommsdorff (2009), A. Kravchenko, I. Turin (2008), S. Attias-Donfut (1995) Kogteva E.V., Kirillina T.Yu. (2017).

The Classical Theories of Generations by K. Mannheim, drawing on the works of V. Deltey and M. Weber, considers generations in the historical-social context as part of a «limited historical period». He emphasizes that each new generation has «a fundamentally new life experience, which is formed in interaction with the social environment».

Mannheim focuses on generational change as a driving force for progress. In his view, in an era of stagnation, intergenerational relations are based on the dominance of older over younger. In a stable situation of socio-cultural development, the generation rather supports traditions than creates new ones. Whereas in an era of instability, older generations are more susceptible to the influence of younger ones [9].

Jose Ortega-i-Gasset linked the development of breeding groups with age and characteristics of their actions. He combines in the concept of «generation» two aspects: sociological (mass) and psychological (individual). Ortega-i-Gasset distinguishes the concepts of «contemporary» and «peer», emphasizing the differences between «unity of time» and «unity of age».

Generation, in his opinion, is a «community of co-existing in the same circle of peers, united by dates of birth and living space» [13]. He also considered that intergenerational transmission is a process of intergenerational succession.

The activity of each generation lasts about 30 years and is divided into two periods: in the first generation it spreads its ideas, inclinations and tastes that become dominant in the second. The main characteristics of a generation are age and the historical context that determines its social roles.

The new theory of generations, created by American scientists Neil Howe and William Strauss (Howe, N., Strauss, W.1991) connect central concepts of the theory of generations - «generation» and «conflict of generations» with socio-psychological characteristics of each generation [2]. They found that in certain periods of time, most people have similar values. This allowed the above authors to describe the collective image of each generation. They define a generation as social and mean by this definition a certain set of people born in the period of twenty years and having similar values and attitudes, and also experiencing the same historical events, it gives the impression of belonging to one generation [3]. The present living representatives belong to the following generations: «silent generation», «baby-boomers», generation «X», «Y» («millennials»), generation Z [2].

Researcher of generations V. Radayev describes the main value orientations and differences inherent in the said generations [15]. Numerous studies, including in sociology and psychology, have shown differences in cultural capital: higher levels of education are found among younger generations, and foreign language proficiency has also increased.

Younger generations consume less alcohol than older ones, giving greater importance to health and healthy lifestyle; this phenomenon has been called «Helsism» (Crawford, 2006; Golman, 2014). They postpone the creation of a family for later dates, which is confirmed by the concept of «late adulthood» (Fry, Igielnik, Patten, 2018; Bialik, Fry, 2019). The birth of children is also postponed. Sociologists have revealed differences between generations in relation to work: unlike the older, young people are oriented towards quick earnings and career success, so they are not afraid of changing jobs. Globalization, population migration and the development of information space have become prerequisites for the transformation of values - from survival values focused on security to values of development and expression where freedom becomes more important, Human rights and equality [15, p.181]

In a study of Kaunenka I.I., conducted on student youth, with the aim of studying intergenerational relations, it was found that they defined themselves as technological («Friendly with new technologies»), having their own position («We have our own opinion», «We

learn faster»), situational. («Living by ourselves»), the desire for self-development («Self-development in the first place»), making unconsidered decisions. («We decide quickly, without thinking about the consequences»). To the question «What do you not understand in your parents? What question would you like to ask?» , young people do not understand why the older generation does not know how to take care of themselves; developed sacrifice; why you must «die» at work; parents have strong stereotypes («What will people say?»; «How can you leave your job?»), not the criticism of the older generation to information [4].

According to the author, the younger generation is positive towards the older, however, intergenerational communication is reduced and new forms are needed for its development, mutual understanding, since intergenerational cultural transmission is a condition and basis of psychological well-being of the person.

Analyzing the definitions of the concept «intergenerational value transmission» described in works by Barni, (2009); Schonpflug, (2001); Trommsdorff (2009), it is possible to define this concept as a transfer of values from one generation to another in the process of socialization of the person. The mechanism of intergenerational transmission is called the process of transfer of values, norms, traditions, experiences from one generation to another [4]. Through this mechanism, the cultural heritage is preserved and the intergenerational relationship strengthened. The transmission of spiritual, moral values is an important function of intergenerational relations. Through intergenerational transmission spiritual capital, moral values, cultural-historical experience, traditions are transmitted. The process is continuous, continuity being ensured by the desire to pass on cultural heritage to the next generations [4]. L. Zharov, V. Kakhanovsky, V. Yakovlev highlighted 3 main forms of transmission of cultural heritage and spiritual values:

1. transfer of the principle of imitation, a model in direct communication with other significant;
2. transfer through norms, installations, prescriptions;
3. An axiological one, in which the values and ideals that prevail in a given society are transmitted.

One of the factors of intergenerational transmission is intra-family social capital, which is perceived by children as a level of social and psychological support from parents. The availability of this capital enriches and facilitates the transfer of values, creating a favourable family climate in which the barriers between generations are weakened [5]. French sociologist K. Aitas-Donfou believes that the family is a place of constant interaction between generations, where both descending and ascending flow of information occurs [1]. It is the family that becomes the core of transmission processes and the main agent of socialization. In the last century, intergenerational transmission was carried out through the family, social and educational institutions, as well as through social groups, church and media. The family is an institution in which it is possible to inculcate and «transmit» values such as trust, tolerance and reciprocity to society as a whole.

The *intergenerational* transmission process performs the following functions:

1. Regulatory - the person regulates its activities in accordance with its value system, which is inherited from previous generations.

2. Informative - the person keeps in memory the history of the nation, family, events, traditions and culture.

3. Unifying - the basis is a common value system for all individuals, which becomes a reference in life.

4. Educational - in the process of transmission norms and rules are transmitted, which contributes to the formation of the personality.

5. Referential - allows to pass on its value system to the following generations.

6. Supporting - Refers to the role of parents in the life of the younger generation and vice versa [7].

Digital technologies are currently shaping forms of social interaction. The term «digital socialization» is introduced relatively recently and denotes the process of obtaining by the individual social experience and connections, mediated by the use of the internet and social networks, acquired in online contexts in the multiple reality of the modern world [16]. In the modern world, the Internet and social networks play a leading role in the process of socialization.

We have been living in an era of transitivity for the last two decades. The transitive society is in between two social states and it is transitory [12]. A basic feature of the transitive society is its internal contradiction. The authors, using the term «social transformation», define transitivity as a state containing social contradictions and transitioning to a new level of existence. On the one hand, this state includes signs of an age that is passing away, on the other - new signs are being born. T. Martsinkovskaya links transitivity with the change of ages, considering this phenomenon as a break, accompanied by a change in the picture of the world [12].

With the increase of speed and freedom of movement, the perception of time and space has changed. The emergence of new information technologies has also transformed the space-time continuum. These changes have affected all spheres of life. The period of socialization has increased. The term «current socialization» describes a change in this process: under conditions of transitivity socialization can be continuous [10]. The processes of intergenerational interactions have changed, in particular the process of value transfer. Values themselves have also undergone transformation. One of the characteristics of a transitive society is the change in value orientation and perceptions. Another characteristic of transitivity is the variability of the situation. Transitivity, affecting all generations, is nevertheless natural for young people and adolescents.

M. Meade described the characteristics of a predominant type of culture, which is especially relevant for our modern world, when adults learn from children and children socialize in new, unknown environment [11]. Term «Prefigurative» implies greater significance of the experience of the younger generation compared to the previous ones, that is, ancestors learn from descendants. So the experience is passed from younger generations to older ones. T. Martsinkovskaya a researcher of transitivity, notes that the processes of intergenerational transmission have been transformed

and the transmission occurs in zigzag fashion: horizontally and vertically, by depth and time [10]. Such changes were first described by 3. Bauman (2008), emphasizing the weakening of ties even in one family. Nowadays, when all the family members are immersed in an information space that differs for different generations, this becomes a cause of intergenerational transmission disruption. Older generations trust television more, while younger generations and their actions are influenced by the internet [10].

One type of intergenerational transmission is the exchange of subcultures. T. Martsinkovskaya defines subculture as a «way of acquiring postnatal identity» and socialization in this group [10. page 28] The author believes that the mechanism of forming subculture is social experiences, related to the definition of values of self-realization. Subculture is seen as a variant of the identity of a particular generation, which brings about differences in the picture of the world, perceptions and values between generations, potentially leading to generational conflicts.

M. Postnikova, based on the analysis of scientific literature, identifies three forms of interaction between generations: conflict, break-up and succession. Conflict can be both intra-generational (between members of the same generation) and inter-generational (between members of different generations). The cause of conflicts between generations is often the opposition of values, ideals and directions of movement in life (social orientation) [14]. Two forms of intergenerational cooperation can be made.

The transitivity of the modern world exacerbates the problem of intergenerational relationships. The new social situation in which young people develop is fundamentally different from the conditions in which their parents, ancestors grew up. These changes concern social connections, information immersion and experience, which reinforces cultural alienation between generations. Modern digital socialization is a new reality, familiar to younger generations. The lower age limit for the use of gadgets continues to decline, and the age range of internet users is expanding. The existing interlocking transmission mechanisms are unique in the past. Intergenerational continuity in transitive society is characterized by abnormality - vagueness and contradiction of norms and values, as well as low degree of influence of social norms [18].

Conclusions

Modern society is undergoing significant changes in the ways of transmitting experience and values between generations. The transformation processes that characterize a transitive society lead to new forms of interaction with reality, which affects all spheres of life, including organization, socialization and communication. The value system is undergoing transformation, which affects the mechanisms of transmission of installations and experiences.

The relevance of intergenerational relations increases in the context of global changes, as the succession of generations is a necessary condition for integration and stabilization of society. Research shows that generational relationships and conflicts are becoming key themes in social sciences. Classics of the theory of

generations, such as K. Mannheim and H. Ortega-i-Gasset, emphasize the importance of historical social context in generation formation and their interaction.

Recent research has shown that young people exhibit different values and attitudes from previous generations, resulting in cultural alienation and a change in intergenerational communication. Digital socialization and technological changes are defining new forms of interaction and require adaptation of existing mechanisms for the transfer of values.

An important part of inter-generational transmission is intra-family social capital, which contributes to the creation of a favourable climate for the transfer of cultural heritage. The main functions of this process include regulating behaviour, preserving historical memory, and nurturing and maintaining intergenerational ties.

Thus, the process of intergenerational transmission in a transient society needs rethinking and adapting to new realities in order to preserve cultural heritage and ensure inter-generational understanding.

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